

N. virescens (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Gonatocerus sp. (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Spiders (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Cyrtorhinus sp. (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Microvelia (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Collembola (no. enclosure⁻¹)

2. Population of common predators of insect pests of rice and collembolans 1DBS and 3 d DAS. Kap Srau, Phnom Penh, Cambodia, 1994 wet season.

increased in both treated and untreated plots by 3 DAS (42 DT). By contrast, the number of *Gonatocerus* spp., an egg parasitoid of *Nephotettix virescens*, declined (Fig. 1). Populations of spiders and collembolans were heavily affected by insecticide applications. The spraying had no effect on the populations of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter and *Microvelia douglasi atrolineata* Bergorth (Fig. 2). Leaf damage was similar (15 and 16%) and yield comparable (2970 ±

209 and 2290 ± 221 kg ha⁻¹) in the treated and untreated plots. The insecticide did not appear to cause significant reduction in pest species and predators such as *Cyrtorhinus* and *Microvelia*. Instead, it had more significant effects on parasitoids, spiders, and collembolans.

It is likely that pest infestations in Cambodia are inherently low, especially in an insect-resistant cultivar like IR72. Methyl parathion applications are thus not justified. ■

Effect of soil amendments on grain yield and incidence of rice leaffolder in iron-toxic soils of north Orissa, India

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In valley areas of north Orissa, India, the incidence of rice leaffolder (LF), *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, and iron toxicity have been of concern in wetland rice production. This field experiment examined the effects of soil amendments on the incidence of LF and the grain yield of two varieties, Lalat and Jajati.

A factorial randomized block design with three replications was laid out in farmers' fields adjacent to the iron ore mines of Joda, Keonjhar (Orissa), India. The soil (Oxic Paleustalf) of the experiment site had a pH of 4.8. The HCl extract of the soil evidenced Fe²⁺ content of 3500 ppm (by ortho phenanthroline method). The treatments consisted of application of various fertilizer rates with organic manure as amendments on 12 × 12-m plots. One-month-old seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 15 × 10 cm on 24 Jul 1993. The percentage of leaf damage caused by the LF in each plot was ascertained at the flag leaf stage by counting the total and infested leaves on 10 random-

Table 1. Leaffolder (LF) incidence and grain yield in response to amendments to iron-toxic soils in rice, irrespective of variety.

Treatment	Leaf damage (%) by LF ^a	Grain yield (tha ⁻¹)
60:13.2:24.9 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	22.6 (27.2)	2.7
T ₁ + cowdung @ 5 t ha ⁻¹	34.6 (35.8)	3.4
T ₁ + MnO (4%) seedling root dip	32.6 (34.7)	2.9
60:13.2:49.8 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	22.6 (28.3)	2.9
60:13.2:74.7 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	25.3 (30.1)	3.0
60:13.2:99.6 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	22.6 (28.1)	2.9
30:13.2:24.9 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + FYM @ 3.3 t ha ⁻¹ + green leaves of <i>Ipomoea</i> @ 1.7 t ha ⁻¹	25.3 (29.9)	2.8
LSD (P=0.05)	3.8	ns ^b

^a Figures in parentheses are in corresponding angular values.

^b ns = not significant.

ly selected hills. Leaf damage ranged from 22.6 to 34.6% and, among the amendments tested, application of cow dung (at 5 t ha⁻¹) or seeding root dip in MnO (4%) appeared to accelerate leaf damage (32.6-34.6%) by LF appreciably (Table 1). Irrespective of soil amendments, however, Lalat suffered less

damage (23.05%) than Jajati (30.1%). Moreover, Lalat yielded significantly more (3.4 t ha⁻¹) than Jajati (2.6 t ha⁻¹) in iron-toxic soils (Table 2). Thus, adoption of a variety such as Lalat might be a possible option for stable rice production by resource-poor farmers working the iron-toxic soils of the region. ■

Table 2. Effect of variety on LF incidence and grain yield, irrespective of soil amendments in iron-toxic soils of north Orissa, India.

Variety	Leaf damage (%) by LF ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Lalat	23.0 (28.2)	3.4
Jajati	30.1 (33.0)	2.6
LSD (P=0.05)	2.0	0.4

^aFigures in parentheses are in corresponding angular values.

Integrated pest management—weeds

Crop rotation in red rice control

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There are currently no chemical weed control options for red rice, the most important weed of irrigated ricefields in Rio Grande do Sul, Brasil. This research evaluated red rice control through crop rotation in highly infested areas. Rotations included no-till or

tilled rice, soybean, and maize during summer and ryegrass or fallow in winter (Table 1). A trifactorial split-plot design was used with three replications. Treatment effects were evaluated by counting seeds within a 10-cm-deep soil layer and by counting the panicles before harvest.

Soybean - maize rotations led to a 82% decrease of the seed reservoir in the soil from 1992 to 1996. Soybean rotation exerted greater control (88%)

than maize (76%). Conventional tillage controlled 93% of the red rice reservoir compared with no tillage at 76%, an amount considered low because of deficient control during the 1993-94 growing season. Continuous rice (S7) had about twice the number of red rice seeds in the soil but reduced by 45% the number of weed panicles at harvest. Based on the number of red rice panicles (Table 2), crop rotation presented 95% average control. Weed control

Table 1. Number of red rice seeds m⁻² in the soil (0-10 cm deep) in areas with ryegrass (c/a) and without ryegrass (s/a) before seeding, Santa Maria, Rio Grande do Sul, Brasil. 1992-96.

Crop sequence ^a	1992-93			1993-94			1994-95			1995-96			% of control
	c/a	s/a	Av										
S1	2261	4843	3552	2041	1200	1620	2814	2418	2616	308	361	334	90
S2	1715	4236	2975	744	960	852	7979	1619	4795	127	117	122	96
S3	2594	3300	2947	1777	1032	1404	6450	5177	5813	647	605	626	79
S4	1484	1052	1268	1368	576	972	2121	2206	2163	435	287	361	72
S5	3026	3069	3047	1633	720	1176	2759	4541	3650	148	244	196	94
S6	2792	2593	2692	840	648	744	3098	1018	2058	1963	153	1061	60
S7	1844	2161	2002	1016	1432	1224	3024	2716	2870	3820	3966	3897	-
Av	2312	3182	2747	1400	856	1128	4203	2829	3516	605	294	450	82

^aS1 = 199192 Rice (c) - soybean (c) - 199293 rice (c) - soybean (c) - 199394 rice (c) - soybean (c) - 199495 rice (c) - soybean (c)
 S2 = 199192 Rice (c) - maize (c) - 199293 rice (c) - maize (c) - 199394 rice (c) - maize (c) - 199495 rice (c) - maize (c)
 S3 = 199192 Rice (d) - soybean (d) - 199293 rice (d) - soybean (c) - 199394 rice (d) - soybean (c) - 199495 rice (d) - soybean (c)
 S4 = 199192 Rice (d) - maize (d) - 199293 rice (d) - maize (d) - 199394 rice (d) - maize (d) - 199495 rice (d) - maize (d)
 S5 = 199192 Rice (c) - soybean (d) - 199293 rice (c) - soybean (d) - 199394 rice (c) - soybean (d) - 199495 rice (c) - soybean (d)
 S6 = 199192 Rice (c) - maize (d) - 199293 rice (c) - maize (d) - 199394 rice (c) - maize (d) - 199495 rice (c) - maize (d)
 S7 = 199192 Rice - rice - 199293 rice - rice - 199394 rice - rice - 199495 rice - rice
 c = conventional tillage, d = no tillage.

Table 2. Number of red rice panicles m⁻² in areas with rye grass (c/a) and without rye grass (s/a) before harvest. Santa Maria, Brazil. 1992-96.

Crop sequence	1992-93			1993-94			1994-95			% of control
	c/a	s/a	Av	c/a	s/a	Av	c/a	s/a	Av	
S1	180	201	190	136	140	138	9	10	9.5	95
S2	118	160	139	104	76	90	7	10.3	8.7	94
S3	265	270	267	135	83	109	4.6	5.3	5	98
S4	23	61	42	63	52	57	3.6	5.3	4.5	89
S5	171	184	177	127	113	120	3	6.3	4.7	97
S6	102	182	142	107	113	110	4.3	2.3	3.3	98
S7	361	389	375	159	164	161	213	198	206	45
Av	143	176	160	112	96	104	5.2	6.6	6.0	95

assisted by soybean or maize rotations as well as by tillage systems were similar and always above 90% during the three seasons. Neither the ryegrass nor fallow during winter months affected the seed reservoir or the quantity of red rice panicles.

Crop rotation is an efficient method to control red rice in lowland areas where efficient herbicides are also used. In the highly infested areas, it is recommended that the weed seed reservoir should be reduced before adopting crop rotations or no tillage. Ryegrass fallow does not contribute to the control of red rice. ■